

The Riesz Representation Operator on the Dual of $C[0; 1]$ is Computable

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Abstract: By the Riesz representation theorem, for every linear functional $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ there is a function $g : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of bounded variation such that

$$F(h) = \int h dg \quad (h \in C[0; 1]).$$

A computable version is proved in [Lu and Weihrauch(2007)]: a function g can be computed from F and its norm, and F can be computed from g and an upper bound of its total variation. In this article we present a much more transparent proof. We first give a new proof of the classical theorem from which we then can derive the computable version easily. As in [Lu and Weihrauch(2007)] we use the framework of TTE, the representation approach for computable analysis, which allows to define natural concepts of computability for the operators under consideration.

Key Words: computable analysis, Riesz representation theorem

Category: F.0, F.1.1

1 Introduction

The Riesz representation theorem for continuous functionals on $C[0; 1]$, the Banach space of continuous functions $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ endowed with the supremum norm, can be stated as follows

[Goffman and Pedrick(1965), Heuser(2006)]:

Theorem 1 (Riesz representation theorem). *For every continuous linear operator $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ there is a function $g : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of bounded variation such that*

$$F(h) = \int h dg \quad (h \in C[0; 1])$$

and

$$V(g) = \|F\|.$$

Here, $\int h dg$ is the Riemann-Stieltjes integral [Schechter(1997)]. The reversal of this theorem is almost trivial: the operator $h \mapsto \int h dg$ is continuous and linear.

A computable version of the Riesz representation theorem has been proved in [Lu and Weihrauch(2007)]: a function g can be computed from F and its norm, and F can be computed from g and an upper bound of its total variation. This proof, however, is complicated and partly intransparent. In this article we present a simpler and much more transparent proof which starts with a new proof of the classical theorem from which the computable version can be derived easily.

The classical Riesz representation theorem can be proved as follows [Goffman and Pedrick(1965), Heuser(2006)]: By the Hahn-Banach theorem, the operator F has a continuous extension \overline{F} to the Banach space $B[0; 1]$ of bounded functions $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $\|F\| = \|\overline{F}\|$. Then define g by $g(x) := \overline{F}(\chi_{[0;x]})$, where $\chi_{[0;x]}$ is the characteristic function of $[0; x]$. In our proof, from F and $\|F\|$ we define a dense set of points x in which g will be continuous. For these points x we can compute F to $\chi_{[0;x]}$, then we define $g(x) := \overline{F}(\chi_{[0;x]})$.

In Section 2 we extend the definition of the Variation and the Riemann-Stieltjes integral to partial functions $g : \subseteq [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the domains of which are dense in the unit interval. We observe that $\int h dg$ can be defined already from any restriction of g to a countable dense subset of it domain.

In Section 3 we introduce the set PC_F of the points x which do not contribute to $\|F\|$ and define $F(\chi_{[0;x]})$ as the limit of $F(h_i)$ where $(h_i)_i$ is a sequence of continuous functions "converging" to $\chi_{[0;x]}$. We prove that g_F is continuous with no continuous proper extension, and that its total variation is $\|F\|$. Furthermore, $F(h) = \int h dg_F$ for all continuous functions $f : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

In Section 4 we shortly summarize the computability concepts used in the following. In particular we define our representation of the functions with countable dense domain and finite variation.

Finally, in Section 5 we prove that from F and $\|F\|$ a restriction g of g_F can be *computed* (a function of bounded variation representing F), and that F can be computed from g and a upper bound of $\text{Var}(g)$.

2 The Riemann-Stieltjes integral

We recall the definition of the Riemann-Stieltjes integral. We study only the special case of functions on the unit interval $[0; 1]$. Results for arbitrary intervals $[a; b]$ can be derived easily from the special case. In our context it seems to be appropriate to generalize the definitions to partial functions $g : \subseteq [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of bounded variation.

A *partition* of the real interval $[0; 1]$ is a sequence $Z = (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n)$, $n \geq 1$, of real numbers such that $0 = x_0 < x_1 \dots < x_n = 1$. The partition Z has *precision* k , if $x_i - x_{i-1} < 2^{-k}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. A partition $Z' = (x'_0, x'_1, \dots, x'_m)$, is finer than Z , if $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \{x'_0, x'_1, \dots, x'_m\}$. Z is a partition for $g : \subseteq [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ if $\{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq \text{dom}(g)$. For a partition Z for g define

$$S(g, Z) := \sum_{i=1}^n |g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})|. \quad (1)$$

The variation of g is defined by

$$V(g) := \sup\{S(g, Z) \mid Z \text{ is a partition for } g\}. \quad (2)$$

The function g is of *bounded variation* if its variation $V(g)$ is finite.

Definition 2. Let BV be the set of (partial) functions $g : \subseteq [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of bounded variation such that $\{0, 1\} \subseteq \text{dom}(g)$ and $\text{dom}(g)$ is dense in $[0; 1]$.

The relation to the usual definitions with total functions g is given by the following lemma.

Lemma 3.

1. Let $g, g' \in BV$ such that g is a restriction of g' . Then $V(g) \leq V(g')$.
2. For every function $g \in BV$ the extension $\bar{g} : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\bar{g}(x) := \lim_{y \in \text{dom}(g), y \nearrow x} g(y) \quad \text{for } x \notin \text{dom}(g) \quad (3)$$

is of bounded variation such that $V(g) = V(\bar{g})$.

Proof: (1) Obvious.

(2) Suppose this limit from below does not exist. Then there is an increasing sequence $(y_i)_i$ converging to x such that the sequence $(g(y_i))_i$ does not converge, hence there is some $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $(\forall i)(\exists j > i) |g(y_i) - g(y_j)| > \varepsilon$. Therefore, for every n there is some partition $Z_n = (0, y_{i_0}, y_{i_1}, \dots, y_{i_n}, 1)$ for g such that $S(g, Z_n) > n \cdot \varepsilon$. But g is of bounded variation, hence $\bar{g}(x)$ exists.

Since $\text{dom}(g) \subseteq \text{dom}(\bar{g})$, $V(g) \leq V(\bar{g})$. On the other hand suppose $X := (0 = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n = 1)$ is a partition for \bar{g} and let $\varepsilon > 0$. For $1 \leq i \leq n$ there are $y_i \in \text{dom}(g)$ such that $x_{i-1} < y_i < x_i$ and $|g(y_i) - \bar{g}(x_i)| < \varepsilon/(2n)$, hence for $Y := (0, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n, 1)$, $|S(\bar{g}, X) - S(g, Y)| < \varepsilon$. Therefore, $V(\bar{g}) \leq V(g)$. \square

On the space $C[0; 1]$ of continuous functions $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the norm is defined by $\|h\| := \sup_{x \in [0; 1]} |h(x)|$. On the space $C'[0; 1]$ of the linear continuous operators $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ the norm is defined by $\|F\| := \sup_{\|h\| \leq 1} |F(h)|$.

In the following let $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function and let $g \in BV$. For any partition $Z = (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n)$ of $[0; 1]$ for g define

$$S(g, h, Z) := \sum_{i=1}^n h(x_i)(g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})). \quad (4)$$

Since h is continuous and its domain is compact, it has a (uniform) *modulus of continuity*, i.e., a function $m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that $|h(x) - h(y)| \leq 2^{-k}$ if $|x - y| \leq 2^{-m(k)}$. We may assume that the function m is non-decreasing.

Lemma 4 [Lu and Weihrauch(2007)]. *Let $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function with modulus of continuity $m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ and let $g \in \text{BV}$. Then there is a unique number $I \in \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$|I - S(g, h, Z)| \leq 2^{-k}V(g)$$

for every partition Z for g with precision $m(k + 1)$.

A proof is given in [Lu and Weihrauch(2007)]. A revised proof is given in the appendix.

Definition 5. The number I from Lemma 4 is called the *Riemann-Stieltjes integral* and is denoted by $\int h dg$.

Notice that by Lemma 4 the integral $\int f dg$ is determined already by the values of the function g on an arbitrary set X that is dense in $\text{dom}(g)$, since there are partitions of arbitrary precision that contain of points only from the set X .

Corollary 6. *Let $g, g' \in \text{BV}$. Suppose $A \subseteq \text{dom}(g) \cap \text{dom}(g')$ is dense in $[0; 1]$ such that $\{0, 1\} \subseteq A$ and $(\forall x \in A)g(x) = g'(x)$. Then $\int h dg = \int h dg'$ for every $h \in C[0; 1]$.*

Proof: Obvious. □

3 Another proof of the classical theorem

In this section we present a proof of the (non-computable) Riesz representation theorem which we will effectivize in Section 5. Let Pg be the (countable) set of of polygon functions $h : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with rational vertices and let $\text{RI} := \{(a; b) \mid a, b \in \mathbb{Q}, 0 \leq a < b \leq 1\}$ be the set of open rational subintervals of $(0; 1)$. By the Weierstraß approximation theorem Pg is dense in $C[0; 1]$. In the following let $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a linear continuous functional.

Definition 7. For $h \in C[0; 1]$, $Y \subseteq [0; 1]$, and $x \in (0; 1)$ define $\text{NZ}(h)$, $\|F\|_Y$ and $\text{PC}_F \subseteq (0; 1)$ as follows:

$$\text{NZ}(h) := \{x \in [0; 1] \mid h(x) \neq 0\}, \tag{5}$$

$$\|F\|_Y := \sup\{|F(h)| \mid h \in C[0; 1], \|h\| \leq 1, \text{NZ}(h) \subseteq Y\}, \tag{6}$$

$$x \in \text{PC}_F : \iff \inf\{\|F\|_J \mid x \in J \in \text{RI}\} = 0. \tag{7}$$

$\text{NZ}(h)$ is the non-zero region of the function h , $\|F\|_Y$ is the contribution of the set Y to $\|F\|$, and $x \in \text{PC}_F$ means that the contribution of $x \in (0; 1)$ to $\|F\|$ is 0. The points from PC_F will be the points of continuity of the associated function g_F of bounded variation.

- Lemma 8.** 1. $\|F\|_Y \leq \|F\|_Z$ if $Y \subseteq Z$,
2. $\|F\|_{J_1} + \dots + \|F\|_{J_n} \leq \|F\|$ if the J_i are pairwise disjoint.
3. $|F(h_1)| + \dots + |F(h_n)| \leq \|F\|$ if $\|h_i\| \leq 1$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and the sets $\text{NZ}(h_i)$ are pairwise disjoint.

Proof: (1) Obvious.

(2) Let $\varepsilon > 0$. For $i = 1, \dots, n$ there is a continuous functions h_i such that $\|h_i\| \leq 1$, $\text{NZ}(h_i) \subseteq J_i$ and $|F(h_i)| \geq \|F\|_{J_i} - \varepsilon$. We may assume $F(h_i) \geq 0$ (if $F(h_i) < 0$, replace h_i by $-h_i$). Since the sets $\text{NZ}(h_i)$ are pairwise disjoint, $\|\sum_i h_i\| \leq 1$. We obtain

$$\sum_i \|F\|_{J_i} \leq n\varepsilon + \sum_i |F(h_i)| = n\varepsilon + \sum_i F(h_i) = n\varepsilon + F(\sum_i h_i) \leq n\varepsilon + \|F\|.$$

This is true for all $\varepsilon > 0$, hence $\sum_i \|F\|_{J_i} \leq \|F\|$.

(3) This follows from (2). □

At most countably many points can have a positive contribution to $\|F\|$.

Lemma 9. The complement $(0; 1) \setminus \text{PC}_F$ of PC_F is at most countable.

Proof: For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let T_n be the set of all $x \in (0; 1)$ such that $\inf\{\|F\|_J \mid x \in J\} > 2^{-n}$. Suppose, $\text{card}(T_n) \geq N > 2^n \cdot \|F\|$. Then there are N points $x_1, \dots, x_N \in T_n$ and pairwise disjoint intervals J_1, \dots, J_N such that $x_i \in J_i$. Since $\|F\|_{J_i} > 2^{-n}$ for all i , $\sum_i \|F\|_{J_i} > N \cdot 2^{-n} > \|F\|$. But this is false by Lemma 8. Therefore, T_n is finite for every n and $(0; 1) \setminus \text{PC}_F = \bigcup_n T_n$ is at most countable. □

We define *slanted step functions* (Figure 2) as approximations of characteristic functions $\chi_{[0;x]}$.

Definition 10. For $I = (a; b) \in \text{RI}$ let $s_I \in \text{Pg}$, the *slanted step function* at I , be the polygon function whose graph has the vertices $(0, 1)$, $(a, 1)$, $(b, 0)$, and $(1, 0)$.

Suppose $J, K \subseteq L$. Then $\text{NZ}(s_J - s_K) \subseteq L$ and $\|s_J - s_K\| \leq 1$, hence $|F(s_J) - F(s_K)| = |F(s_J - s_K)| \leq \|F\|_L$, therefore

$$|F(s_J) - F(s_K)| \leq \|F\|_L \text{ if } J, K \subseteq L. \tag{8}$$

In the classical proof (Section 1) $g(x)$ can be defined as $\overline{F}(\chi_{[0;x]})$, where \overline{F} is the Hahn-Banach extension of F to the bounded real functions. We replace this definition as follows considering only points of continuity:

Definition 11. Define a function $g_F : \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows: $\text{dom}(g_F) := \{0, 1\} \cup \text{PC}_F$, $g(0) := 0$, $g(1) := F(1)$. For $x \in \text{PC}_F$ let $(J_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of rational intervals such that $x \in J_{n+1} \subseteq J_n$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \text{length}(J_n) = 0$. Then let $g_F(x) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(s_{J_n})$.

Since $x \in \text{PC}_F$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|F\|_{J_n} = 0$ by monotonicity in J of $\|F\|_J$. We show that $g_F(x)$ exists and does not depend on the specific sequence $(J_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$.

Lemma 12. *The function g_F is well-defined.*

Proof: For every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is some n such that $\|F\|_{J_n} < \varepsilon$. By (8) for $k > n$, $|F(s_{J_n}) - F(s_{J_k})| \leq \|F\|_{J_n} < \varepsilon$, hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(s_{J_n})$ exists.

Let $(L_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be another sequence of rational intervals such that $x \in L_{n+1} \subseteq L_n$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|F\|_{L_n} = 0$. Then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(s_{L_n})$ exists accordingly. Let $K_n := J_n \cap L_n$. By (8), $|F(s_{J_n}) - F(s_{K_n})| \leq \|F\|_{J_n}$ and $|F(s_{L_n}) - F(s_{K_n})| \leq \|F\|_{L_n}$, hence $|F(s_{J_n}) - F(s_{L_n})| \leq \|F\|_{J_n} + \|F\|_{L_n}$. Therefore, $\lim_n |F(s_{J_n}) - F(s_{L_n})| = 0$ and finally $\lim_n F(s_{J_n}) = \lim_n F(s_{L_n})$. \square

Lemma 13. *Suppose $J, K, L \in \text{RI}$, $J, K \subseteq L$ and $x, y \in \text{PC}_F \cap L$. Then*

$$|F(s_J) - F(s_K)| \leq \|F\|_L, \tag{9}$$

$$|F(s_J) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L, \tag{10}$$

$$|g_F(x) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L. \tag{11}$$

Proof:

(9): By (8).

(10): For every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is some $K \subseteq L$ such that $y \in K$ and $|F(s_K) - g_F(y)| \leq \varepsilon$. Then by (9), $|F(s_J) - g_F(y)| \leq |F(s_J) - F(s_K)| + |F(s_K) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L + \varepsilon$. Therefore $|F(s_J) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L$.

(11): For every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is some $J \subseteq L$ such that $x \in J$ and $|F(s_J) - g_F(x)| \leq \varepsilon$. Then by (10), $|g_F(x) - g_F(y)| \leq |g_F(x) - F(s_J)| + |F(s_J) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L + \varepsilon$. Therefore $|g_F(x) - g_F(y)| \leq \|F\|_L$. \square

We will prove some further properties of the function g_F . In the following, $\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$ abbreviates $\lim_{y \in \text{dom}(g_F), y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$ and $\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y)$ abbreviates $\lim_{y \in \text{dom}(g_F), y \searrow x} g_F(y)$.

Lemma 14. *For all $x \in (0; 1)$,*

1. $\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$ and $\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y)$ exist,

2. $|\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y) - \lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y)| = \inf_{x \in J} \|F\|_J$.

Proof:

(1) Suppose that $\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$ does not exist. Then there is an increasing sequence $(y_i)_i$ from PC_F converging to x such that the sequence $(g_F(y_i))_i$ does not converge, hence there is some $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $(\forall N)(\exists i, j > N) |g_F(y_i) - g_F(y_j)| > \varepsilon$. Therefore, for every N we can find $y_{i_0} < \dots < y_{i_{2N}}$ from the sequence $(y_i)_i$ such that $|g_F(y_{i_{2k}}) - g_F(y_{i_{2k-1}})| > \varepsilon$, for $1 \leq k \leq N$. Hence there are pairwise disjoint rational intervals J_1, J_2, \dots, J_N such that $y_{i_{2k-1}}, y_{i_{2k}} \in J_k$ for $1 \leq k \leq N$. Then by (11), $\|F\|_{J_k} > \varepsilon$ for each $1 \leq k \leq N$. By Lemma 8, $\|F\| \geq \sum_{k=1}^N \|F\|_{J_k} > N \cdot \varepsilon$. Since this is true for all numbers N , $\|F\|$ is unbounded. Contradiction.

(2) Let $a = \inf_{x \in J} \|F\|_J$ and $\delta > 0$. There is some $J \in RI$ such that

$$x \in J \text{ and } |\|F\|_J - a| < \delta. \tag{12}$$

“ \leq ”: By (11) and (12) for $y_1, y_2 \in J \cap PC_F$, $|g_F(y_1) - g_F(y_2)| \leq \|F\|_J < a + \delta$, hence $|\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y) - \lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y)| \leq a + \delta$. Since this is true for all $\delta > 0$, “ \leq ” is true.

“ \geq ”: An example of the functions, intervals etc. defined in the following is shown in Figure 1. There is a rational polygon h such that

$$NZ(h) \subseteq J, \|h\| \leq 1 \text{ and } |F(h) - \|F\|_J| < \delta.$$

The function h can be chosen such that

$$K \subseteq J; \ x \in K \text{ and } (\forall y \in K) h(y) = c \tag{13}$$

for some $K \in RI$ and some c such that $0 < |c| \leq 1$. We may assume $0 < c \leq 1$ (if $c < 0$ replace h by $-h$). There are $y_<, y_> \in K \cap PC_F$, $y_< < x < y_>$ such that

$$|\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y) - g_F(y_<)| < \delta \text{ and } |\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) - g_F(y_>)| < \delta. \tag{14}$$

There are $L, R \in RI$ such that $L, R \subseteq K$, $L < x < R$, $y_< \in L$, $y_> \in R$ and

$$\|F\|_L < \delta \text{ and } \|F\|_R < \delta. \tag{15}$$

Let m_L and m_R be the center of L and R respectively. Let $t_L : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the rational polygon whose graph has the vertices $(0, 0), (\inf L, 0), (m_L, c), (\sup L, 0), (1, 0)$ and let $t_R : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the rational polygon whose graph has the vertices $(0, 0), (\inf R, 0), (m_R, c), (\sup R, 0), (1, 0)$. Then $|F(t_L)| \leq \|F\|_L < \delta$ and $|F(t_R)| \leq \|F\|_R < \delta$.

Let $h' := h - t_L - t_R$. Then

$$|F(h') - F(h)| = |F(t_L) + F(t_R)| \leq 2\delta. \tag{16}$$

Let N be the interval $(m_L; m_R)$. Let h_0 be the polygon function whose graph has the vertices $(0, 0), (m_L, 0), (\sup L, c), (\inf R, c), (m_R, 0), (1, 0)$. Let $\bar{h} := h' - h_0$.

Figure 1: The functions h, h_0 and h'

We will show that $|F(\bar{h})|$ is small and $|F(h_0)| \approx a$. There is some rational polygon function h'_0 such that $\|h'_0\| = 1$, $\text{NZ}(h'_0) \subseteq N$ and

$$\| \|F\|_N - F(h'_0) \| < \delta. \tag{17}$$

There are $\alpha, \beta \in \{1, -1\}$ such that $|F(h'_0)| + |F(\bar{h})| = F(\alpha h'_0) + F(\beta \bar{h}) = F(\alpha h'_0 + \beta \bar{h})$. Since $\text{NZ}(h'_0) \cap \text{NZ}(\bar{h}) = \emptyset$, $\|\alpha h'_0 + \beta \bar{h}\| \leq 1$, hence $|F(h'_0)| + |F(\bar{h})| \leq \|F\|_J \leq a + \delta$. Since $\|F_N\| \leq |F(h'_0)| + \delta$ and $\|F\|_N \geq a$ because of $x \in N$,

$$|F(h') - F(h_0)| = |F(\bar{h})| \leq a + \delta - |F(h'_0)| \leq a + \delta - \|F\|_N + \delta \leq 2\delta.$$

Therefore $F(\bar{h})$ is small. From the above estimations, $|a| \leq |a - \|F\|_J| + \| \|F\|_J - F(h) \| + |F(h) - F(h')| + |F(h') - F(h_0)| + |F(h_0)|$, hence $a \leq \delta + \delta + 2\delta + 2\delta + |F(h_0)|$, that is,

$$a \leq 6\delta + |F(h_0)|.$$

Therefore, $|F(h_0)|$ is big. By construction, $0 < c = \|h_0\| \leq 1$. Let $\hat{h} := h_0/c$. Then $a \leq 6\delta + |F(\hat{h})|$.

Since $\|\widehat{h}\| = 1$, $\widehat{h} = s_T - s_S$ where $S = (m_L; \sup L)$ and $T = (\inf R; m_R)$. By Lemma 13,

$$|g_F(y_<) - F(s_S)| \leq \|F\|_K \quad \text{and} \quad |g_F(y_>) - F(s_T)| \leq \|F\|_K,$$

hence by Lemma 13,

$$\begin{aligned} a &\leq 6\delta + |F(\widehat{h})| \\ &= 6\delta + |F(s_T) - F(s_S)| \\ &\leq 6\delta + |F(s_T) - g_F(y_>)| + |g_F(y_>) - \lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y)| \\ &\quad + |\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) - \lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)| + |\lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y) - g_F(y_<)| + |g_F(y_<) - F(s_S)| \\ &\leq 6\delta + \|F\|_R + \delta + |\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) - \lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)| + \delta + \|F\|_L \\ &\leq |\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) - \lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)| + 10\delta \end{aligned}$$

Since this is true for all $\delta > 0$, “ \geq ” has been proved. \square

Theorem 15.

1. g_F is continuous on $(0; 1) \cap \text{dom}(g_F) = \text{PC}_F$,
2. no proper extension g of g_F is continuous on $(0; 1) \cap \text{dom}(g)$,
3. $\text{Var}(g) = \|F\|$ for every restriction $g \in \text{BV}$ of g_F ,
4. $\text{Var}(g_F) = \|F\|$.

Proof: 1. If $x \in \text{PC}_F$ then $\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) = \lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$ by Lemma 14. Therefore g_F is continuous in x .

2. Let g be an extension of g_F and let g be continuous in $x \in \text{dom}(g)$. Then $\lim_{y \searrow x} g_F(y) = \lim_{y \nearrow x} g_F(y)$, hence $\inf_{x \in J} \|F\|_J = 0$ by Lemma 14, that is, $x \in \text{PC}_F$.

3. **Var**(g) $\leq \|F\|$: Let $X := (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n)$ be a partition for g . Let $\varepsilon > 0$. By the definition of g_F for every $0 < i < n$ there is an interval $K_i \in \text{RI}$ such that $x_i \in K_i$, $\sup K_i < \inf K_{i+1}$, $\|F\|_{K_i} < \varepsilon$. Furthermore, for $0 < i < n$ there are intervals $L_i, R_i \in \text{RI}$ such that $L_i, R_i \subseteq K_i$ and $\sup L_i < x_i < \inf R_i$. Figure 2 shows the intervals and some corresponding slanted step functions. By Lemma 8 and Lemma 13,

$$\begin{aligned} S(g, X) &= |g(x_1)| + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} |g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})| + |g(1) - g(x_{n-1})| \\ &\leq |F(s_{L_1})| + \varepsilon + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (|F(s_{L_i} - s_{R_{i-1}})| + 2\varepsilon) \\ &\quad + |F(1 - s_{R_{n-1}})| + \varepsilon \\ &\leq 2n\varepsilon + \|F\|. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2: The intervals K_i, L_i, R_i and corresponding slanted step functions.

Since this is true for all $\varepsilon > 0$, $S(g, X) \leq \|F\|$. Since this is true for all partitions X for g , $\text{Var}(g) \leq \|F\|$.

3. $\|F\| \leq \text{Var}(g)$: First we show that for every rational polygon function $h_0 \in \text{Pg}$ there are a partition $X = (0 = x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = 1)$ and intervals K_i, L_i, R_i such that for the function h_2 (see Figure 3), $F(h_0)$ is close to $F(h_2)$ if $(x_i - x_{i-1})$ and $\|F\|_{K_i}$ are sufficiently small for all $1 < i \leq n$. By Lemma 13 $F(h_2)$ can be related to $S(g, X)$ (and to $S(g, h_0, X)$ in the proof of Theorem 16).

Let $h_0 \in \text{Pg}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be a modulus of continuity of h_0 . Let $n := 2^{m(k)+1} + 1$. Since $\text{dom}(g)$ is dense, there is a partition $X = (0 = x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = 1)$ for g such that $x_i - x_{i-1} < 2^{-m(k)-1}$. Since all the $x_i \in \text{PC}_F$, for every $0 < i < n$ there are rational intervals K_i, L_i, R_i such that

$$\begin{aligned} x_i \in K_i, \quad 0 < \inf K_1, \quad \sup K_i < \inf K_{i+1}, \quad \sup K_{n-1} < 1, \\ \|F\|_{K_i} < 2^{-k}/n, \\ \inf L_i = \inf K_i, \quad \sup L_i < x_i < \inf R_i \quad \sup R_i = \sup K_i. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3 shows an example of the left end of the unit interval with the function h_0 and the intervals.

For $1 \leq i \leq n$ define

$$c_i := \max\{h_0(x) \mid \sup R_{i-1} \leq x \leq \inf L_i\},$$

(where $\sup R_0 := 0$ and $\inf L_n := 1$). Define a rational polygon function h_1 by the following sequence of vertices:

$(\sup R_0, c_1), (\inf L_1, c_1), (\sup R_1, c_2), (\inf L_2, c_2), \dots, (\sup R_{n-1}, c_n), (\inf L_n, c_n)$ (see Figure 3, notice that c_i may be negative).

Suppose $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $\sup R_{i-1} \leq x \leq \inf L_i$. Then $x_{i-1} \leq x \leq x_i$ and $h_1(x) = c_i = h_0(y)$ for some y with $x_{i-1} \leq y \leq x_i$. Then $|x - y| < 2^{-m(k)}$, hence $|h_1(x) - h_0(x)| = |h_0(y) - h_0(x)| < 2^{-k}$.

Figure 3: The functions h_0, h_1 and h_2 .

Suppose $0 < i < n$ and $x \in K_i$. Then $h_1(x) = h_0(y)$ for some y such that $x_{i-1} < y < x_{i+1}$. Since $x_{i-1} < x < x_{i+1}$, $|x - y| < 2^{-m(k)}$ and hence $|h_1(x) - h_0(x)| = |h_0(y) - h_0(x)| < 2^{-k}$. Therefore, $\|h_1 - h_0\| < 2^{-k}$ and hence $|F(h_1) - F(h_0)| \leq \|F\| \cdot 2^{-k}$.

Let $1 \leq i \leq n$. Then $c_i = h_0(y)$ for some $x_{i-1} \leq y \leq x_i$. Since $|x_i - y| < 2^{-m(k)}$, $|h_0(x_i) - c_i| = |h_0(x_i) - h_0(y)| \leq 2^{-k}$.

From h_1 we construct a third function h_2 by replacing for every $0 < i < n$ the line segment from $(\inf L_i, c_i)$ to $(\sup R_i, c_{i+1})$ in the graph of h_1 by the polygon $(\inf L_i, c_i), (\sup L_i, 0), (\inf R_i, 0), (\sup R_i, c_{i+1})$ (see Figure 3). Then by Definition 10,

$$h_2 = c_1 s_{L_1} + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} c_i (s_{L_i} - s_{R_{i-1}}) + c_n (1 - s_{R_{n-1}}).$$

For $0 < i < n$ let d_i be the polygon function defined by the sequence of vertices $(0, 0), (\inf L_i, 0), (\sup L_i, h_1(\sup L_i)), (\inf R_i, h_1(\inf R_i)), (\sup R_i, 0), (1, 0)$.

Then $h_2 = h_1 - \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} d_i$. Since $\text{NZ}(d_i) \subseteq K_i$ and $\|d_i\| \leq \|h_0\|$,

$$|F(h_2) - F(h_1)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} |F(d_i)| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \|F\|_{K_i} \cdot \|h_0\| \leq \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k}.$$

We prove $\|F\| \leq \text{Var}(g)$. There is some $h_0 \in \text{Pg}$ such that $\|h_0\| \leq 1$ and $\|F\| \leq |F(h_0)| + 2^{-k}$. Since $|c_i| \leq 1$ and by Lemma 13,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|F\| &\leq |F(h_0 - h_1)| + |F(h_1 - h_2)| + |F(h_2)| + 2^{-k} \\
 &\leq \|F\| \cdot 2^{-k} + \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k} + |F(h_2)| + 2^{-k} \\
 &\leq |F(s_{L_1})| + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} |F(s_{L_i} - s_{R_{i-1}})| + |F(1 - s_{R_{n-1}})| \\
 &\quad + (\|F\| + 2) \cdot 2^{-k} \\
 &\leq |g(x_1)| + 2^{-k}/n + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} (|g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})| + 2 \cdot 2^{-k}/n) \\
 &\quad + |g(1) - g(x_{n-1})| + 2^{-k}/n + (\|F\| + 2) \cdot 2^{-k} \\
 &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n |g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})| + 2 \cdot 2^{-k} + (\|F\| + 2) \cdot 2^{-k} \\
 &= S(g, X) + (\|F\| + 4) \cdot 2^{-k} \\
 &\leq \text{Var}(g) + (\|F\| + 4) \cdot 2^{-k}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this is true for all k , $\|F\| \leq \text{Var}(g)$.

4. This follows from 3. □

Theorem 16. *Let $g \in \text{BV}$ be a restriction of g_F . Then for every $h \in C[0; 1]$, $F(h) = \int h \, dg$.*

Proof: Let $h \in C[0; 1]$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$. There is a function $h_0 \in \text{Pg}$ such that $\|h - h_0\| \leq 2^{-k}$. Let $m, n, X, K_i, L_i, R_i, c_i, h_1, h_2$ be the objects introduced in the proof of Theorem 15.3. We prove that $|F(h) - S(g, h, X)|$ is small. By the results that we have already shown,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |F(h) - F(h_2)| &\leq |F(h) - F(h_0)| + |F(h_0) - F(h_1)| + |F(h_1) - F(h_2)| \\
 &\leq \|F\| \cdot 2^{-k} + \|F\| \cdot 2^{-k} + \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k} \\
 &= (2\|F\| + \|h_0\|) \cdot 2^{-k}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $|F(s_{R_i}) + B| \leq |g(x_i) + B| + \|F\|_{K_i}$ etc. by Lemma 13, $c_i \leq \|h_0\|$, and $|h_0(x_i) - c_i| \leq 2^{-k}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|F(h_2) - S(g, h_0, X)| \\
 &\leq \left| c_1 F(s_{L_1}) + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} c_i (F(s_{L_i}) - F(s_{R_{i-1}})) + c_n (F(1) - F(s_{R_{n-1}})) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \sum_{i=1}^n h_0(x_i) (g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \left| c_1 g(x_1) + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} c_i (g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) + c_n (g(1) - g(x_{n-1})) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \sum_{i=1}^n h_0(x_i) (g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) \right| \\
&\quad + |c_1| \|F\|_{K_1} + \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} |c_i| (\|F\|_{K_i} + \|F\|_{K_{i-1}}) + |c_n| \|F\|_{K_{n-1}} \\
&\leq \left| \sum_{i=1}^n (c_i - h_0(x_i)) (g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) \right| + 2 \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k} \\
&\leq \sum_{i=1}^n |c_i - h_0(x_i)| \cdot |g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})| + \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k+1} \\
&\leq 2^{-k} \cdot S(g, X) + \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k+1} \\
&\leq 2^{-k} \cdot \text{Var}(g) + \|h_0\| \cdot 2^{-k+1} \\
&= (\|F\| + 2 \|h_0\|) \cdot 2^{-k}
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore,

$$\begin{aligned}
|S(g, h_0, X) - S(g, h, X)| &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^n (h_0(x_i) - h(x_i)) (g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) \right| \\
&\leq 2^{-k} \sum_{i=1}^n |g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})| \\
&= 2^{-k} \cdot S(g, X) \\
&\leq 2^{-k} \cdot \text{Var}(g) \\
&= 2^{-k} \cdot \|F\|.
\end{aligned}$$

Combining these results we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
|F(h) - S(g, h, X)| &\leq |F(h) - F(h_2)| + |F(h_2) - S(g, h_0, X)| + |S(g, h_0, X) - S(g, h, X)| \\
&\leq (2\|F\| + \|h_0\|) \cdot 2^{-k} + (\|F\| + 2\|h_0\|) \cdot 2^{-k} + 2^{-k} \cdot \|F\| \\
&\leq (\|F\| + \|h\| + 1) \cdot 2^{-k+2}
\end{aligned}$$

Since X has precision $m(k)$, $|\int h dg - S(g, h, X)| \leq \text{Var}(g) \cdot 2^{-k+1}$ by Lemma 4. Therefore, $|F(h) - \int h dg| \leq (3\|F\| + 2\|h\| + 2) \cdot 2^{-k+1}$. Since this is true for all k , $F(h) = \int h dg$. \square

4 Concepts from Computable Analysis

For studying computability we use the representation approach (TTE) for Computable Analysis [Weihrauch(2000), Brattka et al.(2008)]. Let Σ be a finite al-

phabet. Computable functions on Σ^* (the set of finite sequences over Σ) and Σ^ω (the set of infinite sequences over Σ) are defined by Turing machines which map sequences to sequences (finite or infinite). On Σ^* and Σ^ω finite or countable tupling will be denoted by $\langle \rangle$ [Weihrauch(2000)]. The tupling functions and the projections of their inverses are computable.

In TTE, sequences from Σ^* or Σ^ω are used as “names” of abstract objects such as rational numbers, real numbers, real functions or points of a metric space. We consider computability of multi-functions w.r.t. multi-representations [Weihrauch(2000)], [Brattka et al.(2008)], [Weihrauch(2008), Sections 3,6,8,9].

A representation of a set X is a function $\delta : \subseteq C \rightarrow X$ where $C = \Sigma^*$ or $C = \Sigma^\omega$. If $\delta(p) = x$ we call p a δ -name of x . If $f : X \rightrightarrows Y$ is a multi-function (on represented sets) then $f(x)$ is the set of $y \in Y$ which are accepted as a result of f applied to x . (Example: $f : \mathbb{R} \rightrightarrows \mathbb{Q}$, $f(x) := \{a \in \mathbb{Q} \mid x < a\}$, we may say: “the multi-function f finds some rational upper bound of x ”.)

For representations $\gamma : \subseteq Y \rightarrow M$ and $\gamma_0 : \subseteq Y_0 \rightarrow M_0$, a function $h : \subseteq Y \rightarrow Y_0$ is a (γ, γ_0) -realization of a multi-function $f : \subseteq M \rightrightarrows M_0$, iff for all $p \in Y$ and $x \in M$,

$$\gamma(p) = x \in \text{dom}(f) \implies \gamma_0 \circ h(p) \in f(x). \tag{18}$$

Fig. 4 illustrates the definition.

Figure 4: $h(p)$ is a name of some $y \in f(x)$, if p is a name of $x \in \text{dom}(f)$.

The multi-function f is called (γ, γ_0) -computable, if it has a computable (γ, γ_0) -realization and (γ, γ_0) -continuous if it has a continuous realization. The definitions can be generalized straightforwardly to multi-functions $f : M_1 \times \dots \times M_n \rightrightarrows M_0$ for represented sets M_i .

For two representations $\delta_i : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow M_i$ ($i = 1, 2$) the canonical representation $[\delta_1, \delta_2]$ of the product $M_1 \times M_2$ is defined by

$$[\delta_1, \delta_2](p_1, p_2) = (\delta_1(p_1), \delta(p_2)). \tag{19}$$

For two representations $\delta_i \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightrightarrows M_i$ ($i = 1, 2$), $\delta_1 \leq \delta_2$ (δ_1 is reducible to δ_2) iff there is a computable function $h : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \Sigma^\omega$ such that $(\forall p \in \text{dom}(\delta_1)) \delta_1(p) = \delta_2 h(p)$. (If p is a δ_1 -name of x then $h(p)$ is a δ_2 -name of x .)

We use various canonical notations $\nu : \subseteq \Sigma^* \rightarrow X$: $\nu_{\mathbb{N}}$ for the natural numbers, $\nu_{\mathbb{Q}}$ for the rational numbers, ν_{Pg} for the polygon functions on $[0; 1]$ whose graphs have rational vertices, and ν_I for the set RI open subintervals $(a; b) \subseteq (0; 1)$ with rational endpoints. For functions $m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ we use the canonical representation $\delta_{\mathbb{B}} : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \mathbb{B} = \{m \mid m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}\}$ defined by $\delta_{\mathbb{B}}(p) = m$ if $p = 1^{m(0)}01^{m(1)}01^{m(2)}0\dots$. For the real numbers we use the Cauchy representation $\rho : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\rho(p) = x$ if p is (encodes) a sequence $(a_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ of rational numbers such that for all i , $|x - a_i| \leq 2^{-i}$. By the Weierstraß approximation theorem the countable set of Pg of polygon functions with rational vertices is dense in $C[0; 1]$. Therefore, $C[0; 1]$ with notation ν_{Pg} of the set Pg is a computable metric space [Weihrauch(2000)] for which we use the Cauchy representation δ_C defined as follows: $\delta_C(p) = h$ if p is (encodes) a sequence $(h_i)_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ of polygons $h_i \in \text{Pg}$ such that for all i , $\|h - h_i\| \leq 2^{-i}$ [Weihrauch(2000)]. For the space $C(C[0; 1], \mathbb{R})$ of the continuous (not necessarily linear) functions $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we use the canonical representation $[\delta_C \rightarrow \rho]$ [Weihrauch(2000), Weihrauch and Grubba(2009)]. It is determined uniquely up to equivalence by **(U)** and **(S)**:

- (U)** the function $\text{APPLY} : (F, h) \mapsto F(h)$ is $([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \delta_C, \rho)$ -computable,
- (S)** if for some representation δ of a subset of $C(C[0; 1], \mathbb{R})$, APPLY is (δ, δ_C, ρ) -computable then $\delta \leq [\delta_C \rightarrow \rho]$.

(U) corresponds to the “universal Turing machine theorem” and **(S)** to the “smn-theorem” from computability theory. Roughly speaking, $[\delta_C \rightarrow \rho]$ is the “poorest” representation of the set $C(C[0; 1], \mathbb{R})$ for which the APPLY function becomes computable.

For converting the classical proof mentioned in Section 2 we needed a representation of the set $B[0; 1]$ of bounded functions $g : [0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Since it has a cardinality bigger than that of Σ^ω , it has no representation. To overcome this difficulty it would suffice to extend F to the Banach space $B_1[0; 1]$ generated by the continuous functions and all the characteristic function $\chi_{[0; x]}$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$. However, since this space is not separable we do not know any reasonable representation of it. We solve the problem by (implicitly) extending F only to functions $\chi_{[0; x]}$ from a countable dense set of points x in which g is continuous and for which we can compute $g(x) := \overline{F}(\chi_{[0; x]})$ from F and $\|F\|$. Remember

that every function of bounded variation has at most countably many points of discontinuity.

Finally, for formulating a computable version of the Riesz representation theorem we need a representation for functions of bounded variation. In our context the only application of a function g of bounded variation is to compute the Riemann-Stieltjes integral $\int h \, dg$ for continuous functions h . By Corollary 6, it suffices to know g on a countable dense set containing 0 and 1. Therefore it will suffice to consider only functions from BV with countable domain.

Definition 17. Let $\text{BVC} := \{g \in \text{BV} \mid \text{dom}(g) \text{ is countable}\}$. Define a representation $\delta_{\text{BVC}} : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow \text{BVC}$ as follows: $\delta_{\text{BVC}}(p) = g$ iff there are sequences $p_0, q_0, p_1, q_1, \dots \in \Sigma^\omega$ such that $p = \langle \langle p_0, q_0 \rangle, \langle p_1, q_1 \rangle, \dots \rangle$, $\rho(p_0) = 0$, $\rho(p_1) = 1$ and $\text{graph}(g) = \{(\rho(p_i), \rho(q_i)) \mid i \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

Informally, a δ_{BVC} -name of g is a list of its graph. For proving computability of multi-functions on represented sets we use “generalized Turing machines” (GTMs) [Tavana and Weihrauch(2011)]. We call a generalized Turing machine M on represented sets *computable*, if all multi-functions on the represented sets occurring in M are computable. We use the following result: the multi-function f_M computed by a computable GTM M on represented sets is computable.

For a representation $\delta : \subseteq \Sigma^\omega \rightarrow Z$ a subset $Y \subseteq Z$ is δ -r.e., iff there is a Type-2 machine N such that for all $p \in \text{dom}(\delta)$,

$$N \text{ halts on input } p \iff \delta(p) \in Y.$$

And $Y \subseteq Z$ is δ -decidable, iff Y and $Z \setminus Y$ are δ -r.e. [Weihrauch(2000)]. As an example, $x < y$ for real numbers is $[\rho, \rho]$ -r.e.

5 The computable Riesz representation theorem

In the following “computable”, “recursively enumerable” and “decidable” means computable, recursively enumerable and decidable, respectively, w.r.t. the notations and multi-representations mentioned in Section 4.

First, from F and $\|F\|$ we will compute some $g \in \text{BVC}$ such that $F(h) = \int h \, dg$. By the next lemma for every rational interval I we can compute subintervals J with arbitrarily small $\|F\|_J$.

Lemma 18. *There is a computable multi-function*

$$e : (F, z, I, n) \mapsto J$$

that maps every continuous linear functional $F : C[0;1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, its norm z , every open rational interval $I = (a; b) \subseteq [0;1]$ and every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ to some open rational interval J such that $\bar{J} \subseteq I$, $\text{length}(J) \leq 2^{-n}$ and $\|F\|_J \leq 2^{-n}$.

Precisely speaking, the multi-function e is $([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \rho, \nu_I, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \nu_I)$ -computable.

Proof: By Lemma 9 there is some $x \in I$ such that $x \in PC_F$. By Definition 7 there is some $J, x \in J \in RI$, such that $\overline{J} \subseteq I$, $\text{length}(J) \leq 2^{-n}$ and $\|F\|_J \leq 2^{-n}$. We show that the multi-function e is $([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \rho, \nu_I, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \nu_I)$ -computable.

For $F, z = \|F\|, I = (a; b), n \in \mathbb{N}, J \in RI$ and $\overline{f} \in Pg$ consider the conditions

$$\overline{J} \subseteq I, \text{ length}(J) \leq 2^{-n}, \tag{20}$$

$$\overline{f}(x) = 0 \text{ for } x \in J, \tag{21}$$

$$\|\overline{f}\| \leq 1, \tag{22}$$

$$|F(\overline{f})| > \|F\| - 2^{-n}. \tag{23}$$

Conditions (20-22) are decidable (relative to their representations). Since $x < y$ is $[\rho, \rho]$ -r.e. and $(F, \overline{f}) \mapsto F(\overline{f})$ is computable, (23) is r.e. Therefore, here is a Type 2-machine M that halts on input $(p_1, p_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6)$ iff

$(F, \|F\|, I, n, J, \overline{f}) := ([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \rho, \nu_I, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \nu_I, \nu_{Pg})(p_1, p_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6)$ satisfies (20-23). From M a Type-2 machine N can be constructed which on input (p_1, p_2, u_3, u_4) (by the usual step counting technique) searches for (u_5, u_6) such that M halts on input $(p_1, p_2, u_3, u_4, u_5, u_6)$.

First we show that $J = \nu_I(u_5)$ and $\overline{f} = \nu_{Pg}(u_6)$ exist.

Since Pg is dense in $C[0; 1]$, $\|F\| = \sup\{|F(h)| \mid h \in Pg, \|h\| \leq 1\}$. Therefore, there is a function $h \in Pg$ with $\|h\| \leq 1$ such that $|F(h)| > \|F\| - 2^{-n-1}$. As we have shown (replace above n by $n + 1$) there is a rational interval $L \subseteq I$ such that $\text{length}(L) \leq 2^{-n}$ and $\|F\|_L \leq 2^{-n-1}$. Let $(a_2; b_2) \subseteq L$ such that h has no vertex in $(a_2; b_2)$. Let $a_1 := a_2 + (b_2 - a_2)/3, b_1 := b_2 - (b_2 - a_2)/3$ and $J := (a_1; b_1)$. Define a function $f_0 \in Pg$ by its vertices as follows:

$$(0, 0), (a_2, 0), (a_1, h(a_1)), (b_1, h(b_1)), (b_2, 0), (1, 0)$$

and let $\overline{f} := h - f_0$. Then $\|f_0\| \leq 1$ and $|F(f_0)| \leq 2^{-n-1}$ since $NZ(f_0) \subseteq L$. Since h and f_0 have no vertex in the interval $(a_2; a_1)$, $|h(x) - f_0(x)| \leq |h(a_2)| \leq 1$ for $a_2 \leq x \leq a_1$, correspondingly $|h(x) - f_0(x)| \leq 1$ for $b_1 \leq x \leq b_2$, and $|h(x) - f_0(x)| = 0$ for $a_1 \leq x \leq b_1$. We obtain $\|\overline{f}\| \leq 1$. Furthermore,

$$|F(\overline{f})| = |F(h - f_0)| \geq |F(h)| - |F(f_0)| \geq \|F\| - 2^{-n}.$$

Therefore, J and \overline{f} exist.

It remains to show that J has the properties requested in the lemma. Obviously, $\overline{J} \subseteq I$ and $\text{length}(J) \leq 2^{-n}$. Suppose $h \in C[0; 1], \|h\| \leq 1$ and $NZ(h) \subseteq J$. Since $NZ(h)$ and $NZ(\overline{f})$ are disjoint and of norm ≤ 1 , by Lemma 8, $|F(h)| + |F(\overline{f})| \leq \|F\|$ hence $|F(h)| \leq \|F\| - |F(\overline{f})| < 2^{-n}$. Therefore, $\|F\|_J \leq 2^{-n}$. \square

By iterating the function e from Lemma 18 in every open rational interval we can find some point $x \in \text{PC}_F$ and the value $g_F(x)$.

Lemma 19. *The multi-function $G : (F, \|F\|, I) \rightrightarrows (x, g_F(x))$ mapping F , its norm and an interval $I \in \text{RI}$ to $(x, g_F(x))$ for some $x \in I \cap \text{PC}_F$ is computable.*

Proof: Let $J_{-1} := I$. For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let J_n be a result of applying the multi-function e from Lemma 18 to $(F, \|F\|, J_{n-1}, n)$. Then $(J_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a properly nested sequence of intervals with $\text{length}(J_n) \leq 2^{-n}$. It converges to some point $x \in I$. Since for all n , $x \in J_n$ and $\|F\|_{J_n} \leq 2^{-n}$, $x \in \text{PC}_F$. Furthermore, by Lemma 13, $|g_F(x) - F(s_{J_n})| \leq 2^{-n}$. Therefore $(F(s_{J_n}))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges fast to $g_F(x)$.

Let M_1 be a computable GTM computing the multi-function e from Lemma 18. From M_1 we can construct a computable GTM that on input $(F, \|F\|, I, n)$ computes in turn some J_0, J_1, \dots, J_n and then $(J_n, F(s_{J_n}))$ as its result.

By [Weihrauch(2008), Theorem 35] the multi-function $(F, \|F\|, I) \rightrightarrows (J_n, F(s_{J_n}))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is computable (where the canonical representation considered for sequences [Weihrauch(2000)]). Since the limit operations for nested sequences of intervals converging to a point and for fast converging Cauchy sequences of real numbers are computable [Weihrauch(2000)], $(x, g_F(x))$ can be computed from $(J_n, F(s_{J_n}))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. Therefore, the multi-function G is computable. \square

We can now prove our computable version of the Riesz representation theorem.

Theorem 20 (computable Riesz representation).

The multi-function $\text{RRT} : (F, \|F\|) \rightrightarrows g$ mapping every functional $F : C[0; 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and its norm to some function $g \in \text{BVC}$ such that

- $F(h) = \int h dg$ (for all $h \in C[0; 1]$),
 - g is continuous on $\text{dom}(g) \setminus \{0, 1\}$,
 - $g(0) = 0$ and $\|F\| = \text{Var}(g)$
- is $([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \rho, \delta_{\text{BVC}})$ -computable.*

Proof: Let L_0, L_1, \dots be a canonical numbering of the set RI of open rational intervals. By Lemma 19 there is a computable function G' mapping $(F, \|F\|, n)$ to some $(x_n, y_n) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ where $(x_0, y_0) = (0, 0)$, $(x_1, y_1) = (1, F(1))$ and $(x_n, y_n) \in G(f, \|F\|, L_n)$ if $n \geq 2$. Since $x_n \in \text{PC}_F$ and $y_n = g_F(x_n)$ for all $n \geq 2$, $\{(x_n, y_n) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is the graph of a restriction g of g_F . Since $\{x_n \mid n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is dense, $g \in \text{BVC}$. By Theorem 15, g is continuous on $\text{dom}(g) \setminus \{0, 1\}$ and $\text{Var}(g) = \|F\|$. Obviously, $g(0) = 0$. By Theorem 16, $F(h) = \int h dg$ (for all $h \in C[0; 1]$).

By the type conversion theorem [Weihrauch(2008), Theorem 33], the multi-function $(F, \|F\|) \rightrightarrows ((x_n, y_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is $([\delta_C \rightarrow \rho], \rho, [\nu_{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow [\rho, \rho]])$ -computable. From a $[\nu_{\mathbb{N}} \rightarrow [\rho, \rho]]$ -name of the sequence $((x_n, y_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}} = ((x_0, y_0), (x_1, y_1), \dots)$

we can compute a $[\rho, \rho]^\omega$ -name [Weihrauch(2000), Lemma 3.3.16] which is a δ_{BVC} -name of g . \square

Finally, we prove that a reverse of the Riesz representation theorem is computable.

Theorem 21. *The operator $T : (g, l) \mapsto F$, mapping every $g \in \text{BVC}$ and every $l \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\text{Var}(g) \leq 2^l$ to the functional F defined by $F(h) = \int h dg$ for all $h \in C[0; 1]$, is computable.*

Proof: First we show that $(G, l, h) \mapsto \int h dg$ is computable. By Theorem 6.2.7 in [Weihrauch(2000)] a modulus $m : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ of continuity of h can be computed from h . let ν_{fs} be a canonical notation of the finite sequences of natural numbers. The set of all $(g, (i_1, \dots, i_{n-1}), j)$ such that $(0, x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_{n-1}}, 1)$ is a partition for g of precision j is $(\delta_{\text{BVC}}, \nu_{\text{fs}}, \nu_{\mathbb{N}})$ -r.e. There is computable GTM on represented sets which on input (g, j) finds a sequence (i_1, \dots, i_{n-1}) such that $(0, x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_{n-1}}, 1)$ is a partition for g of precision j . Therefore from (g, h, k, l) we can compute a sequence (i_1, \dots, i_{n-1}) such that $X := (0, x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_{n-1}}, 1)$ is a partition for g of precision $m(k+l+1)$. By Lemma 4, $|\int h dg - S(g, h, X)| \leq 2^{-l-k}V(g) \leq 2^{-k}$. The function $(g, h, X) \mapsto S(g, h, X)$ is computable (by a computable GTM). Therefore, from (g, l, h, k) a number y_k can be computed (multi-valued) such that $|\int h dg - y_k| \leq 2^{-k}$. By [Weihrauch(2008), Theorem 33] the multi-function $(g, l, h) \mapsto (y_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is computable. By [Weihrauch(2000), Theorem 4.3.7], $(g, l, h) \mapsto \int h dg$ is $(\delta_{\text{BVC}}, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}, \delta_C, \rho)$ -computable. By [Weihrauch(2000), Theorem 3.3.15], $(g, l) \mapsto F$ such that $F(h) = \int h dg$ is $(\delta_{\text{BVC}}, \nu_{\mathbb{N}}, [\delta_C \rightarrow \rho])$ -computable. \square

By Theorem 20, from F and $\|F\|$ we can compute g such that $\text{Var}(g) = \|F\|$, and by Theorem 21, from g and an upper bound of $\text{Var}(g)$ we can compute F .

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Appendix

Proof of Lemma 4

Since there are partitions for g of arbitrary precision, I is unique if it exists. Next, we prove

$$|S(g, h, Z_1) - S(g, h, Z_2)| \leq 2^{-k}V(g). \tag{24}$$

for any two partitions Z_1, Z_2 for g with precision $m(k + 1)$.

Let $Z_1 = (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and let Z' be a refinement of Z_1 . Z' can be written as

$$x_0 = y_0^1, y_1^1, \dots, y_{j_1}^1 = x_1 = y_0^2, y_1^2, \dots, y_{j_2}^2 = x_2 \dots \dots = y_0^n, y_1^n, \dots, y_{j_n}^n = x_n$$

($j_1, \dots, j_n \geq 1$). Then

$$\begin{aligned} & |S(g, h, Z_1) - S(g, h, Z')| \\ &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^n h(x_i)(g(x_i) - g(x_{i-1})) - \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} h(y_l^i)(g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)) \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^n h(x_i) \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} (g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)) - \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} h(y_l^i)(g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)) \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} (h(x_i) - h(y_l^i))(g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} |h(x_i) - h(y_l^i)| |g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)| \\ &\leq 2^{-k-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^{j_i} |g(y_l^i) - g(y_{l-1}^i)| \quad \text{since } |x_i - y_l^i| \leq 2^{-m(k+1)} \\ &\leq 2^{-k-1}V(g) \end{aligned}$$

Now let Z' be a common refinement of Z_1 and Z_2 . Then $|S(g, h, Z_1) - S(g, h, Z_2)| \leq |S(g, h, Z_1) - S(g, h, Z')| + |S(g, h, Z') - S(g, h, Z_2)| \leq 2^{-k}V(g)$.

There is a sequence $(Z_k)_k$ of partitions for g such that Z_k has precision $m(k+1)$. By (24) for $j > k$, $|S(g, h, Z_k) - S(g, h, Z_j)| \leq 2^{-k}V(g)$. Let I be the limit of the Cauchy sequence $(S(g, h, Z_k))_k$. Let Z be a partition of precision $m(k+1)$. Then for every $i > k$ by (24),

$$\begin{aligned} |I - S(g, h, Z)| &\leq |I - S(g, h, Z_i)| + |S(g, h, Z_i) - S(g, h, Z)| \\ &\leq 2^{-i}V(g) + 2^{-k}V(g), \end{aligned}$$

hence $|I - S(g, f, Z)| \leq 2^{-k}V(g)$. □